

6.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v1.1

smartdroplets.eu

6.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2

Author(s)/Organisation(s)	Olivera Stojilovic-Foodscale Hub; Stavros Tsitouras-Foodscale Hub
Contributor(s)	Dimitris Fotakidis-Foodscale Hub Grigoris Chatzikostas-Foodscale Hub Despina Kabouridou -Foodscale Hub Leah D. Rotsia-Foodscale Hub Nefeli Raftopoulou-Foodscale Hub
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SMART DROPLETS CONSORTIUM			
PARTICIPANT NUMBER	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION NAME	SHORT NAME	COUNTRY
1	GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON	AUA	GR
2	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY	WU	NL
3	FUNDACIO EURECAT	EUT	ES
4	FONDACIJA VIZLORE LABS	VLF	SRB
5	FOODSCALE HUB GREECE ASSOCIATION FOR ENTREPREUNERSHIP AND INNOVATION ASTIKI MI KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIREIA	FSH	GR
6	AGREENCULTURE	AGC	FR
7	AGRIFOOD LITHUANIA DIH	AFL	LT
8	PETKOS ANONYMI ETAIREIA	AGROMA SA	GR
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Project acronym: Smart Droplets

Topic: HORIZON-CL4-2021-DIGITAL-EMERGING-01-09

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
EC	European Commission
SFTs	Smart Farming Technologies
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
DIS	Direct Injection System
DEC	Dissemination, communication, and exploitation
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
KERs	Key Exploitable Results

1. Introduction

1.1. Project Summary

The Smart Droplets project focuses on supporting the further development of Smart Farming Technologies (SFTs) that are considered key-enablers for farmers to better monitor their crops and reduce the use of chemicals (fertilizers and plant protection products) as well as to reduce GHG emissions, to enable reaching the Green Deal targets towards reduction of agrochemicals. To this end, the Smart Droplets project introduces a novel approach for crop care tasks, by connecting key-technological aspects during open field spraying and is committed to advancing both hardware and software capabilities during the chemical application, in order to meet the sustainability scope of the EU Green Deal and the recently reformed Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). Smart Droplets' solution relies upon implementing the Autonomous retrofit tractors with Direct Injection System (DIS) for intelligent spraying - avoiding exposure of farmers to hazardous chemicals. Through the combination of high-level technologies (>TRL 7), Smart Droplets adopts a hybrid approach for spraying operations, combining Data/AI/Digital Farm Twin technologies designed to translate data into actionable information, and real-time data collected from Field demonstrators evaluating and demonstrating optimized technologies in the real environments. Ensuring replicability and uptake of digital technologies by deploying innovative tools, services, and recommendations while making them relevant and of practical use to farmers, advisors, and policymakers across Europe; Smart Droplets will test the solution on two diversified and complementary environments, namely apple orchard and wheat farms. Moreover, Smart Droplets Academy will run each year, engaging and educating non-experts stakeholders operating within the agricultural vertical on AI, AI ethics, Data and Agrifood Robotics. The Smart Droplets Consortium consists of all agricultural AI, data, and robotics value chain actors, and is well-balanced in terms of expertise, entity type, and geographical distribution necessary to meet its objectives.

1.2. Document Scope

The Dissemination, communication, and exploitation (DEC) plan and reports provides the guidelines for effectively sharing information within the consortium and an extensive strategy for transferring project knowledge and results to the targeted stakeholders. This document is the first iteration and represents the preliminary plan of the DEC plan and reports which will be updated to monitor the plan's implementation (M12, M24, M42).

1.3. Document Structure

This document is comprised of the following chapters:

Chapter 1 provides a summary of the project, with the document scope and its overall structure for better comprehension and readability.

Chapter 2 provides an overview of the project's key outcomes, as well as the dissemination and communication strategy with the corresponding timeliness and target groups.

Chapter 3 dives into the specific dissemination and communication activities, tools and channels developed and to be used through the duration of the project's implementation including the visual identity, communication material, and channel mix.

Chapter 4 outlines and explains the specified reporting and monitoring procedures and tools used to track progress; namely focusing on KPIs.

Chapter 5 defines the initial entry point of the project's exploitable results while keeping in mind their detailed expansion and elaboration in deliverable *D6.5 Sustainability, Scalability & IPR management strategy v1* in M6.

Chapter 6 presents the conclusions of the deliverable.

Annex A provides the logo variations of Smart Droplets that will be used for different media.

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Annex B presents Smart Droplets' social media banners that will be used on the website and social media.

Annex C provides images of the dissemination and communication material that has already been designed for the Smart Droplets brand including shirts, hoodies, stickers, a banner, the press release template, and others.

Annex D is the document created to keep track of each partner's social media pages.

2. Overview

2.1. Project Aim and Outcome

In recent years, agricultural environments are characterized by rapid changes, while **crop care** tasks have always been repetitive, tedious, and potentially hazardous exposing farmers to health risks that should be avoided. Consequently, the sector is shifting towards more selective treatment applications to improve the quality and efficiency of chemical spraying while simultaneously benefiting workers in this sector as well as the planet.

In the case of **crop spraying operations**, AI models, data, and exploitation of autonomous robotic systems have not reached a mature technological level, mainly due to the lack of a holistic approach that combines physical and digital assets for optimal field performance and minimal environmental impact. AI and Data and robotic advances on SFTs can contribute to fulfilling this ambition, bringing benefits in terms of reduced pesticide use, low carbon emissions, low water use, and reduced food waste, thus enabling environmental sustainability.

Smart Droplets' therefore aims is to advance both hardware and software capabilities during chemical applications for resource optimization and minimization of chemical waste. To accomplish this vision, this project will use already existing technologies (>TRL 7) developed within but not limited to the agricultural industry.

Figure 1 Smart Droplets concept approach

The Smart Droplets consortium consists of **9** partners across **6** countries bringing together experts in **SFTs** (e.g., Direct Injection Spraying (DIS), Digital twins, data infrastructures, AI models), in **agricultural issues** (e.g., CAP, pesticide application, environmental assessment) and **social sciences** (e.g., business performance metrics, communication activities, marketing, training, and capacity building).

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Smart Droplets will engage a multi-actor approach and feedback-driven solution by strengthening and utilizing the 2 farm pilot test cases to contribute to the project's 3 key major outcomes grouped in the following dimension:

- **Innovative AI, data, and robotics solution:** A mix of robotic and non-robotic components focusing on resource optimization and waste reduction when applying chemicals achieved by using state-of-the-art concepts on planning and navigation for the retrofit tractor along with AI, computer vision, and process-based agronomic models.
- **Optimised AI, data, and robotics:** The use of AI-assisted techniques to teach the Digital Farm Twin with high generalization capacity across diverse weather conditions and geographic and site-specific, multi-chemical spraying system for better monitoring of sprayers efficiency and targeted crop interventions.
- **Robotics solutions in harsh environments:** Capability of the solution to localize itself in the environment properly through a 3D localization and mapping solution tailored to the challenges found in agriculture.

Figure 2 Smart Droplets timeline

2.2. Methodology

A robust DEC plan is fundamental for creating lasting impact and will provide a concrete roadmap for partners in order to boost the growth of the Smart Droplets ecosystem, raise awareness of the project activities and maximize impact among key stakeholders and target groups at the broader social, policy, and industry level.

The Smart Droplets DEC plan is inspired by the **SOSTAC model** which includes the following key elements: Situation Analysis, Objectives, Stakeholders & Strategy, Methods & Activities, Control through concrete KPIs.

Situation Analysis: A state-of-play analysis in which the current challenges are highlighted to be addressed by the project, the consortium's expertise, the scientific, societal, and economic impacts during and after the project, and the potential IPR of the results are identified and explained.

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Objectives: The DEC plan will elaborate upon clear and measurable objectives that will be achieved through the implementation of communication, dissemination, and exploitation measures.

Stakeholders & Strategy: Identification of target groups and key messages for effective communication strategy.

Methods & Activities: The DEC plan will build upon the activities, tools, and channels defined in the proposal and include the contributions expected from partners and their distribution over the duration of the project. Open Science practices will be factored into all aspects of DEC implementation.

Control: Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) with specific targets determined during the proposal will be used to monitor the progress of the DEC implementation. Templates for partner reporting will also be used together with digital tools for record keeping, all of which will be presented in the chapter.

Figure 3 Smart Droplets DEC plan

2.2.1. Multi-actor Approach

Smart Droplets will use a multi-actor approach, taking into account all relevant forms of experience and knowledge from a diverse set of partners and stakeholders to achieve the project aims and ensure broad communication from the beginning. It will also extend to the creation and implementation of the DEC plan, which means:

- Translating materials into partner's languages when applicable and favourable;
- Focusing on communicating information that matters to the information recipient;
- Using language, vocabulary, and communication channels that are appealing and audience appropriate;
- Seeking synergies and collaboration opportunities with other projects, initiatives, and networks, with and between academia, industry, society, and government;
- Capitalizing on partners' existing connections, networks, and programs;
- Fostering knowledge exchange activities and discussion.

Figure 4 Smart Droplets multi-actor approach

2.3. Specific Objectives and Time Plan

In order to provide a verifiable trajectory geared towards clear milestones and an estimated deadline the DEC plan objectives are **S.M.A.R.T** (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-Bound). The objectives

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below are used as the structural backbone of the DEC plan and are divided into dissemination and communication objectives.

Dissemination Objectives

- Bring a critical mass of stakeholders and maximize outreach opportunities for Smart Droplets with targeted messaging and customized content
- Diffuse scientific and technological knowledge generated during Smart Droplets and put it to productive use via capacity building
- Nurture a collaboration framework for complementarities/synergies with projects, initiatives, and pan-European networks of DIHs and capitalise on the results
- Get feedback from key stakeholder segments and potential users to make sure our developments are going in the right direction and iterate
- Align and integrate dissemination, communication, community building activities with exploitation efforts to ensure sustainability of reusable assets
- Encourage smooth exploitation of Smart Droplets solution and seamless entry to market

Communication Objectives

- Pair focused content marketing and community-building strategies;
- Raise awareness, facilitate information exchange and capacity building on data-driven sustainability-oriented technology innovations;
- Encourage their acceptability by farmers, their advisors, policymakers;
- Reflect gender equality and inclusivity in the approach, tools and channels.

Phases

A division of the DEC plan into four phases (Figure 5) was crucial, ensuring both its successful implementation and the completion of the aforementioned objectives. The four phases of the DEC plan (Phase 1: Mission, Strategy, Vision, Phase 2: Raise Awareness, Phase 3: Synergies and Network Multipliers, Phase 4: Post-project Sustainability & Impact) last from the beginning of the project until after its end, enhancing post-project sustainability.

Figure 5 Smart Droplets DEC phases figure

2.4. Target Groups

The categorization of interested parties into target groups allows for proper identification and grouping based on interest to the projects and its results. To summarize the benefit to each group, key messages have been

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created (Table 1) and the general breakdown of activities and channels meant to engage each group have been defined (Table 2).

Target Groups	Members	Key Messages
Tech Manufacturers and System Integrators	Industrial automation equipment, robotics, tractors manufacturers, sprayer manufacturers, hardware, robot system integrators, software and middleware developers	Be at the forefront of digital agriculture, enter new markets, expand portfolios and network with end users, researchers and policymakers.
Farmers	Apple farmers, Wheat farmers; farmers in Spain and Lithuania, European farm managers/ administrators/farmers, all types of farmers/farming activities that require/apply fertilization and/or pesticides through spraying	Unlock the potential of SFTs and understand what is truly efficient, sustainable & economical at crop management level.
Agri-food Extension service providers	Public & private service providers, and agricultural consultants; other AKIS actors	Offer clients the most up-to-date knowledge and tools for selecting, using SFTs for crop management
AI/Data/Robotics providers	AI Associations, Data/Robotics Associations	Support businesses in their digital transformations and promote cooperation between industry and agriculture through AI, data and robotics.
Researchers & Academia	EIP-AGRI & Thematic Networks; EIP-AGRI Operational Groups, SWG SCAR-AKIS, Multi-actor projects & Platforms	Contribute to cutting-edge research in digital agriculture and take advantage of interdisciplinary opportunities and collaborations between similar goal-oriented projects.
EDIH/DIHs/ AI, Data and Robotics Innovation Networks	Afrigoood, Robotics, AI, Deep-tech DIHs, Machinery DIHs, European Robotics Network, The European Robotics Research Infrastructure Network, ELISE	Gain first-hand opportunities to work with and test ground-breaking AI and robotics technologies and bring new opportunities to your DIHs members.
Policy Makers and Regulators	Agricultural & env. authorities; CAP governance bodies (e.g., paying agencies & certification bodies); standardization bodies; EU's DG AGRI, DG ENV, Public Env. monitoring authorities	Implement digital agriculture-centred policies based on evidence and farm data and monitor/evaluate the sustainability and impact of those policy measures at the farm, regional, national level.

Table 1 Smart Droplets target groups and their key messages

DC Activities/ Channels	Target Groups						
	Tech Manufacturers & System Integrators	Farmers	Agrifood Extension service providers	AI/Data/ Robotics providers	Researchers & Academia	DIHs/AI/Data & Robotics Innovation Networks	Policy Makers and Regulators
High-level events and campaigns	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓
Community & ecosystem building	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Sustainability & Internal Comms	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	
Full Branding & Web Design	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 2 Smart Droplets target groups and corresponding DC activities/channels

3. Dissemination and Communication Channels, Tools and Activities

3.1. Visual Identity

When taking into account the creation of a project's visual identity it is not merely just the development of the logo or even the website, it is the coherent message delivered and understood between all of the project's multimedia. In order to create a cohesive, easily understandable, and long-lasting visual identity for Smart Droplets and consequently ensure that Smart Droplets stands out with its missions and vision a **brand identity** with all the necessary components was created. Smart Droplet's visual identity has been designed to shape the project's brand, and **reflect the core values and goals** while serving and assisting visually in the delivery of key messages throughout the 42 months of operation of the project. The visual identity serves the core function of allowing the members of the project's consortium to prepare communication material in a coherent way.

The visual identity includes a logo as well as templates and guidelines for the partners on the rules of using the communication elements aimed at promoting the Smart Droplets project and properly acknowledging EU funding.

The digital products that have been created and are foreseen to be derived, including the online media presence and offline materials are and will be made coherent in order to create brand awareness among the targeted audience. The visual identity guidelines are in line with the obligations of beneficiaries regarding information and communication and dissemination measures included in Article 17.2 — Visibility — European flag and funding statement and 17.3 Quality of information — Disclaimer of the Grant Agreement Nr.

3.1.1. Logo

The logo is a tool of essential importance for visual recognition and it is the main tool to create instant identification of the Smart Droplets project. Therefore, the logo was designed keeping in mind the need for

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simplicity and easy recognition yet providing uniqueness while giving a hint of the story about the project itself. The Smart Droplets logo includes the name of the project as its main concept using a clear and modern font and icons representing digital technologies/innovations, symbols easily correlated to the agricultural sector and is optimized for both web and print. The logo will also be used in all internal and external communication and dissemination activities (project website, presentations, flyers, press releases, etc.) to help enhance brand continuity and raise awareness. Several logo variations have been selected for different uses (Annex A). The most frequently use logo for most of the communication and dissemination material is shown in the figure below:

Figure 6 Smart Droplets most used logo

The color palletted was selected to represent the project's values: agriculture, technology, open communication and courage. The colors are optimized for use on both screen (RGB) and print (CMYK) and the contrast is high enough for black-and-white printing.

Figure 7 Smart Droplets colors

To increase project's recognition, extra graphics (covers), that will accompany the Smart Droplet's logo on the website and the social media accounts of the project, have been designed (Annex B) to create a maximum recognition value for our target audiences. This way of coherent communication makes Smart Droplets recognizable and easily differentiable in the social media domain.

3.1.2. EU Emblem

All Smart Droplets dissemination and communication material will acknowledge the requirements set out by the European Union and include the EU flag, the source of funding at the Grant agreement number 101070496.

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Figure 8 EU recognition visual

3.1.3. For Publication

In addition to the EU Emblem, all dissemination and communication material must include the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

3.1.4. Templates

As mentioned in the introduction Smart Droplets aims and will be presented in numerous events, conferences, meetings as well as other occasions to disseminate project developments and results. A presentation template (ppt) has been designed in line with the Smart Droplets graphic identity in order to maintain consistency, and professionalism and promote its recognition. The presentation template can be seen below.

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Figure 9 Smart Droplets presentation template

Another important template for the proper and coherent execution of the Smart Droplets' visual identity is the deliverable template. The Smart Droplets deliverable template is also consistent with the communication and dissemination material (graphic identity) and will be used by the consortium partners for the development of all project deliverables. The deliverable template has a cover page that displays the project's logo in a prominent position, its acronym, deliverable information (number, full title, the work package number and consequent information, document history, dissemination level, and title), Smart Droplets consortium list with the legal notice and funding information, table of content, list of abbreviations, space for the coherent and organised text, as well as the templates for tables and figures ensuring consistency with all deliverables. The deliverable template can be seen in the image below.

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Figure 10 Smart Droplets deliverable template

3.2. Communication Material

Smart Droplets communication material has been designed and prepared to deliver and promote the needed public awareness of the project and include both digital and physical forms to increase public perception and the overall domain of the project's influence. Creating both the online and offline (physical material) Smart Droplets ensures that its mission and vision and the related outcomes reach the needed target audience with ease and efficiency. The major advantage of offline communication is the physical, tangible dimension of occupying space to captivate the needed audience during a project's participation in events, conferences, and other manifestations. The project's roll-up banner will be used to promote and present the project at physical meetings and gatherings and a promotional kit has been created including stickers, face masks, folders, and pens that will be distributed to attract a larger audience (Annex C). Posters, brochures and fact sheets are also additional material created for better communication and idea raising on the project for online and offline situations. The previously mentioned communication material has been designed in order to fit with all of Smart Droplets' groups while communicating our objectives and mission in a fun, understandable and engaging way. Materials such as this are focused and geared toward creating initial awareness about the project, its aims, activities, and results. It should be pointed out that, as a best practice, it is beneficial to follow certain rules when utilizing offline material – regardless of the strategies to be implemented, e.g.: well-prepared headlines, wide use of colors, focus on the benefits – and keeping the tone and the message aligned to the intended target audience. To achieve this goal, a brand book has been developed, to make sure that the produced communication material is in line with the project's visual identity.

3.3. Smart Droplets Channels

3.3.1. Website

The Smart Droplets website (<https://smartdroplets.eu/>) has already been developed and the landing page of the website was released on (M2). The project's website serves the purpose of the primary communication and dissemination platform and enables target groups and Smart Droplets' stakeholders access to the project development and results, and to see and assess the added-value and the impact of digital solutions in agriculture. The development of the site is an ongoing process and will require contributions from all partners for successful updating. The project website will host all public dissemination deliverables, and promote relevant content (news, editorials, videos, events, etc.) for key stakeholder groups, thus engaging them in the content and objectives of the project. The website will also host digital visualizations of project processes and results, to make them accessible to a wider audience. The addition of this content relies fully on the progress of the projects, and will thus be updated and expanded as the project evolves. Finally, the website will also be mobile-friendly, increasing accessibility and maximizing the impact of the project.

Figure 11 Smart Droplets website

The Smart Droplets website has a twofold role:

- i) it will serve as the principal reference point, explaining the project's aims, providing new updates, documents for download, and enabling access to social media accounts of the project
- ii) it will act as a resource centre for research on topics related to digital agricultural technologies, providing important updates that have an impact.

Delivered in M3 and within the scope of this deliverable, the Smart Droplets website is hosted at <https://smartdroplets.eu> and contains the following sections and features.

- **Home/Landing page**

Includes the project logo, image, project graphics, social media icons (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, SlideShare, YouTube, Instagram), a button for sign-up in the Smart Droplets newsletter and a navigation menu providing easy access to information on the project.

- **About us**

This section of the website has quick facts about the project, the expected impact that is to be updated as the project evolves, and objectives.

- **Meet our partners**

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A list of consortium partners, accompanied by a short description of their role in the project, their expertise is provided in this section of the website.

- **Pilots**

A short description of all the two pilots that will assess SFTs and spraying solutions under real conditions is explained. This part of the website is envisioned as a live and continuously growing section that is to be expanded once the project enters the pilot-driven months.

- **Resources**

This section of the website will house all 'ready-to-print material including posters, brochures, project factsheets, notebook, folder, roll-ups, banners, stickers, and a printable brand book and guidelines. Additionally, this segment will house links to public project deliverables deposited on Zenodo as well as The Open Access publications that will be created during the project's lifespan, ensuring far higher citation counts for academic publications and reports, greater impact due to increased visibility with practitioners and the wider stakeholder community and improve the likelihood that future research and analysis will be able to build on and reuse project's results rather than start ab initio, thereby helping in terms of reproductivity and continuity of research results

- **Newsroom**

Press releases and posts will be the main content presented here and will inform stakeholders of all project's activities and upcoming events.

- **Contact us**

All the contact information of the Smart Droplets project will be available under this section enabling the easiest communication with our stakeholders through email (info@smartdroplets.eu).

- The **Privacy Policy**, together with the **Terms and Conditions** have also been included in the Smart Droplets website, set for the general rules and policies governing the visitors' use of the website.

3.3.2. Social Media

The project aims to have a strong social media presence and establish two-way communication channels, to better reach out and interact with target audiences and the broader public. To enhance interactive communication, six (6) media channels were selected based on the following three factors:

- 1) **The most cost-effective** set of channels for sharing immediate updates from the project to all stakeholders' groups;
- 2) **The most adequate, valid and powerful** media channels for spreading and influencing with novel practices, a wide spectrum and number of key-stakeholders;
- 3) **The most popular** social media platforms used by Smart Droplets' partners, to communicate and interact with their customers and other stakeholders.

Smart Droplets is registered and active (M3) on LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, SlideShare, YouTube and Instagram, and has established metrics for each channel to monitor its effectiveness and implement mitigation measures when necessary.

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Figure 12 Different Smart Droplets' social media channels

Smart Droplets takes into account and will thus rely upon the consortium's already developed social media networks (both private and businesses related) to maximize the impact of project's events and outcomes. In this context consortium members are expected to share, comment, publish, and retweet - this depends on the form of social media outlet - content from the Smart Droplets social media accounts and website. Such partner-driven communication efforts also positively result in increased traction for project-related work while increasing traffic on partner's websites and social media. Partners are also encouraged to create relevant content to the project's actions and share it through their channels. A template was created (Annex D) to gather all the needed information from each partner such as the links to their official social media accounts.

After selecting the most favourable and appropriate channels for Smart Droplets several parameters listed below should be considered and used as guidelines when creating social media content and they go as follows:

- I. **INTERACTIVITY** - represents the main pillar of the created social media content and through interactivity, audiences are engaged smoothly and easily. Posts will be easily understood by different target groups and mostly by non-specialists creating traction and engagement.
- II. **EYE-CATCHING** - visually appealing social media posts are more likely to engage an audience than those who are heavily burdened with text. By prioritizing the creation of visuals and graphics Smart Droplets will gain a unique dimension online and will overall lead to higher engagements.
- III. **ADAPTABILITY** - is important as users are opting for the utilization of multiple devices for the viewing of the same content. Thus, the adaptability of social media assets to the format and functioning of several devices is necessary to ensure the maximization of asset placement, especially taking into account the use of mobile phones.

Another important tool for enhanced social media presence is the use of hashtags. Creating relevant hashtags helps users stay in touch with the project and its outcomes while also making it easy to find Smart Droplets-generated knowledge. Hashtags convey the main topics of Smart Droplets into easily digestible and engaging keyword phrases and that helps increase visibility in the social media environment while making key messages stand out and influence the relevant communities. Hashtags also have internal benefits to the consortium, as they will help track and analyse quantitative and qualitative data generated on the above-mentioned social media platforms. For the generation of hashtags, feedback will be asked and received by all project partners, in order to safeguard that the bulk of concepts, ideas, tools/services are captured and incorporated. The project will have official distinctive hashtags seen in the Figure below, which are used to monitor the posts related to the project. The preliminary consortium hashtags in Smart Droplets communication are as follows:

Figure 13 Smart Droplets hashtag cloud

Additionally, to effectively share information on social media our consortium will design posts based on how the audience consumes the message, taking into account user responses and engagements. The following figure explains the steps that a visually appropriate social media post shall contain and based on these high-efficiency posts will be created during project’s lifespan:

Figure 14 Assessment and criteria used to create Smart Droplets social media posts

3.3.2.1. LinkedInLinkeln

A LinkedIn profile (<https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/smart-droplets/>) was created to network with the Smart Droplets’ target audiences and promote the project’s activities.

As such, all the project’s news will be published on its LinkedIn profile and partners will have the opportunity to start conversations on particular themes to attract a wider audience. Figure below provides an overview of Smart Droplets’ LinkedIn profile.

6.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2

Figure 15 Smart Droplets LinkedIn

3.3.2.2. Facebook

Smart Droplets' Facebook page (<https://www.facebook.com/SmartDroplets>) was developed to communicate directly with target audiences on an individual level.

6.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2

Figure 16 Smart Droplets Facebook

3.3.2.3. Instagram

Smart Droplets' Instagram account (<https://www.instagram.com/smartdroplets/>), will be used for communicating with members of the general public. To effectively utilize this social media platform for communicating the scope and objectives of the project, Smart Droplets will post pictures and videos from the meetings and summarised events including that of the two pilot cases once the timeline fits.

6.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2

Figure 17 Smart Droplets Instagram

3.3.2.4. Twitter

A Twitter account was created (<https://twitter.com/SmartDroplets>) to increase the visibility of the project and engage specific audiences such as policy makers and advisors. Smart Droplets will use short messages (less than 280 characters) to interact with them, and post news, events and updates on the project's status.

Twitter's popularity and concise, simple format makes it extremely important and useful for informing and engaging with our targeted audiences and their respective communities. Twitter will also be used to connect to 'high influencers' in the research and business topics of the Smart Droplets project to successfully build an active community.

6.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2

Figure 18 Smart Droplets Twitter

3.3.2.5. SlideShare

A SlideShare account (<https://www.slideshare.net/SmartDroplets>) has been created and the material that is projected to be uploaded are visual formats that will help to resonate more with our readers, reach an audience that is interested in our content and cultivate more opportunities for future collaborations.

Figure 19 Smart Droplets SlideShare

3.3.2.6. YouTube

YouTube (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC4el1fcol5HBhXLvMfAWdvA>) will be used in order to host and promote the Smart Droplets videos, which will be of wide variety, such as interviews, promotional videos, insights from the real-life pilots.

6.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2

Figure 20 Smart Droplets YouTube

3.3.3. Newsletter

An electronic newsletter will be published on a quarterly basis, once every three months to provide updates and relevant information to subscribers and consortium members. This will include the latest developments, partners' features, test case results and activities as well as upcoming events, workshops, demonstrations and where to find recent reports and publications.

Subscriptions can take place on the Smart Droplets website. It should be highlighted that Smart Droplets, will pay special attention to security and respect of the privacy and confidentiality of the user's personal data and newsletter recipients will be asked to provide their consent prior to sending any information related to the project. All relevant activities and aspects related to personal data will be fully compliant with the applicable national, European and international legal framework, and the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation 2016/6798. Interested parties will be able to subscribe and unsubscribe at any given point from the Smart Droplets Newsletters and all the collected data will be stored and saved in the responsible partner's servers. These data will not be accessible from other third parties. To achieve a broader distribution and facilitate the engagement of as many stakeholders as possible, the Smart Droplets partners will be encouraged to promote the newsletters to their contacts who may be interested in the project.

Figure 21 Smart Droplets Newsletter subscription

The first draft of the newsletter will be produced by FSH, with content provided by partners, and will be sent to all consortium partners for review after its completion. The partners will provide their feedback and then FSH will publish the newsletter on the site and promote it to all social media accounts of the project. All newsletters

6.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2

will also be uploaded and remain available on the project's website. As mentioned above, newsletters will be published on a quarterly basis, once every three months and the project anticipate 1.500 newsletter subscribers over the course of the project.

The proposed structure of each newsletter is:

1. Introduction
2. Project Update / Key news, deliverables and project events
3. News & Events
4. Resources for further reading (suggested by all partners + social media input)
5. Spotlight features.

This is a preliminary newsletter structure and is subject to alteration and changes based on consortium agreement and the content produced.

3.3.4. Press Outreach

Press releases will be produced and distributed for publication among national/regional/EU press to further promote the project, its latest activities and developments to a broader audience as well as address more specific stakeholders. The press release will be available on the Smart Droplets website under the tab News Room, and all related publications will be shared on social medial channels to disseminate the information. Thus, a press release template has been developed (Annex C) during M3. To maximize our influence on local stakeholders, the consortium is advised to translate all press releases into all 6 of the consortium partners' languages. More specifically:

Number of partners covered by language	Language
3	Greek
1	Dutch
2	Spanish
2	Serbia
1	French
1	Lithuanian

Table 3 Number of different languages Smart Droplets press releases can be translated into

3.3.5. Publications

In order to have a fully developed communication and dissemination portfolio Smart Droplets takes into account the much-needed impact to be generated in the scientific domain, and more importantly will integrate itself into the development of several scientific, industry and policy publications as well as practice abstracts. Such publication will target the more technical experts of the targeted stakeholder groups and thus promote the projects and its findings among them. The consortium will put an effort for the majority of publications to implement Open Access and open peer review, in accordance with current EU regulations on Open Access and Open Science. Thus, publications will be potentially published in Open Research Europe and/or open-access journals (green or gold). A key aspect for Open Science is to make collected data available for future research

6.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2

and analysis, while avoiding the exposure of any personal data without consent. The availability of project outputs as Open Access will ensure:

1. far higher citation counts for academic publications and reports;
2. greater impact due to increased visibility with practitioners and the wider stakeholder community (in this project above all farmers and advisors);
3. improve the likelihood that future research and analysis will be able to build on and reuse our results rather than start ab initio, thereby helping in terms of the reproducibility and continuity of research results.

3.3.5.1. Scientific publications

Smart Droplets will strive to publish at least **5** peer-reviewed papers & conference contributions in respected and highly rated journals and scientific magazines. Scientific publications are one of the key means of disseminating the project's results to the research community and providing scientific credibility for the project's work. This task will be undertaken mostly by the university and research partners and publications will cover several fields of the work performed within the Smart Droplets project, including but not limited to the results of the two pilots, the testing and success of the developed technologies.

3.3.5.2. Industry publications

Besides the creation of Press Releases and scientific publications, Smart Droplets aims to publish **30** articles in agriculture and related impactful industry magazines, to make the project and its results are known to the industrial stakeholders. To maximize impact, guidelines and timing for identifying, selecting and producing publications using have been defined:

Figure 22 Smart Droplets article submission process

3.3.5.3. Recommendations & statements

The uptake of agricultural innovations is in need for the bottom-up approaches of feedback and recommendation integration in order to design the needed policy measures. In that sense Smart Droplets will produce **2** sets of standardization recommendations from findings developed and tested during the project in order to enable an understating and positive impact of deep tech in agricultural environments while targeting policy personnel and experts. Furthermore, during the project Smart Droplets consortium will create **5** joint press releases/statements with digital agriculture technology initiatives & networks to further influence decision-making and development in agricultural value chains.

6.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2

3.3.5.4. Technical Briefs

Smart Droplets will produce 5 tech briefs in Robotic, Data & AI magazines/publications. The goal is to develop short summaries that describe the main information/recommendation/practice regarding the deployment of deep-tech in agriculture that can be used by the end-users in order to enhance the sustainability performance and competitiveness of the agricultural sector.

3.3.6. Event Planning

For the Smart Droplets projects, the necessary event planning will take part in two phases. The initial phase is the logging and documentation phase. Twice a year, that is on a 6-month period, an event planning form will be sent to the consortium partners to report on the events that are already in their calendars. Partners are expected to provide the following information: a brief description including the date, location, target groups and a preliminary suggestion as to the role/implication for Smart Droplets (i.e., workshop, booth). Gathering information on relevant events will support decision making of event planning. Nevertheless, the form will be sent to partners, and the responses will be compiled using an online reporting tool for easy reference and record-keeping. Several potential events have already been identified and can be seen in Table

The second phase involves the selection of events as seen from Figure 22. This will be done based on the guidelines shown below. When selecting the events for Smart Droplets to participate in the alignment with the project's objectives and budget should be taken into consideration as well as the need to adapt to the individual activities of each partner.

Event	Date	Location	Target groups	Potential Smart Droplets involvement
<u>FRUI ATTRACTION 2023</u>	Fall 2023	Madrid	Industry Farmers/advisors Policy Researchers	Exhibitions
<u>ECPA Conference on Precision Agriculture</u>	Summer 2023	Bologna, Italy	Researchers, Advisors	Paper or poster presenter Attendee
<u>International VDI Conference - Smart Farming</u>	Spring 2023	Dusseldorf Germany	Industry Farmers/advisors Policy Researchers	Speaker Paper or poster presenter Attendee
<u>Congress of EU farmers</u>	Fall 2023	TBD	Farmers Advisors	Speaker

Table 4 Some relevant events for Smart Droplets

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Figure 23 Smart Droplets event selection flow

3.3.7. Networking and Synergies

Building synergies and expanding the Smart Droplets ecosystem is a significant priority of the DEC plan. Much of the project's work will build upon the experience, knowledge and/or data developed by partners during other projects. This collaborative approach will be extended to the DEC and will involve a three-step process.

Phase 1: Identification

Potentially mutually beneficial partnerships and synergies will first be identified, building on the list provided in Table 5. A template for partners to complete, requesting information on any other project's/networks or initiatives they are currently participating in that could be relevant to Smart Droplets, will also be used and embedded during the identification phase. This template will be distributed every 6 months to account for new projects that are beginning. A preliminary list is included in the Table below. Smart Droplets will consider both projects that are near completion and those that will run in parallel. Connecting with projects that will be ending, will provide network expansion opportunities for Smart Droplets while enabling the other projects to meet sustainability goals and keep the momentum of their project going. Projects, networks and initiatives running in parallel will provide several opportunities to strengthen communication pathways and conduct joint activities.

Relevant projects for Smart Droplets	
	Integrated disease management and optimization of spraying in perennial crops and open-field vegetables http://optima-h2020.eu/the-project/
	AI, robotics, and automation in agriculture https://robs4crops.eu/
	Building a European ecosystem for the effective adoption of robotic technologies in the agri-food sector https://agrobfood.eu/visioning-the-future-of-agri-food-robotics/

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Relevant projects for Smart Droplets	
	Autonomous precision spraying tool integrated into a modular unmanned tractor for steep slope vineyards https://scorpion-h2020.eu/
	Portable photonic miniaturised smart system for on-the-spot food quality sensing https://phasmafood.eu/
	Accelerating adoption of IoT for securing sufficient, safe, and healthy food and to strengthen competitiveness of farming and food chains in Europe. https://www.iof2020.eu/
	European federation of Data Driven Innovation Hubs for data driven innovation and experimentation. https://euhubs4data.eu/

Table 5 Relevant projects for Smart Droplets

Phase 2: Evaluation

To ensure synergies will benefit the project and align with Smart Droplets objectives, each potential project, initiatives and network will be assessed against qualitative/quantitative indicators such as:

- Relevance;
- Estimated impact (e.g., visibility, added value);
- Feasibility (e.g., timeline and resources);
- Terms for collaboration, etc.

The results of the evaluation will be consolidated together with the information provided by partners and a final decision will be made by the consortium.

Phase 3: Contact

Once it has been agreed upon that a synergy should be established, the most appropriate approach for making contact will be decided on a case-by-case basis.

Phase 4: Action

Communication pathways and joint activities will be decided after discussions with their representatives and the Smart Droplets consortium and will include (but are not limited to):

- Joint communication, dissemination and exploitation activities;
- Joint policy events;
- Coordinating research and/or joint publications;
- Sharing data, inputs and/or outputs;
- Participation in the other's events;

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- Links to project and project events on website, social media.

3.3.8. EC Tools

Smart Droplets will take advantage of several of the tools offered by the European Commission to support dissemination (D), exploitation (E) and communication (C) of the project's results.

Figure 24 The channels and value EC tools for Smart Droplets

4. Monitoring and Evaluation

4.1. KPIs

In order to successfully monitor the development and progress of the Smart Droplets projects Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are used as concrete, measurable targets for monitoring and evaluating the project's progress and enabling adaptation when necessary. A set of dissemination and communication KPIs and targets have been identified and presented in the following tables for easy distinction amongst partners and the commission:

#	Dissemination KPIs	Target
D.1	Showcase events	
D.1.1	Market & industry events	15
D.1.2	Open days	6

6.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2

#	Dissemination KPIs	Target
D.1.3	“Spotlight on... “Live & On-Demand webinars	6
D.1.4	Solution Showcase and final event	1
D.2	Scientific outreach and technical publications	
D.2.1	Peer-reviewed papers & conferences contributions	5
D.2.2	Tech briefs in Robotic, Data & AI magazines/publications	5
D.3	Networking, synergies & liaison activities	
D.3.1	Representations in WGs	3
D.3.2	Representations alliances	>5
D.3.3.	Joint activities with EU initiatives/ projects	>10
D.4	Contribution to policy measures and standardization efforts	
D.4.1	Joint press releases/ statements	5
D.5	Ecosystem building	
D.5.1	Connections established with DIHs connected to AI.	5

Table 6 Dissemination KPIs for Smart Droplets

#	Communication KPIs	Target
C.1	Full branding and web design	
C.1.1	Printable brand book and guideline	1
C.1.2	Website	1
C.1.3	Social media accounts	6
C.1.4	Coordinated materials (poster, brochures, fact sheet)	3x
C.1.5	Notebook, folder, roll-ups, banners and stickers	1x
C.1.6	Social media kit (feed and story templates, virtual background)	1x
C.2	Digital and Social Media	
C.2.1	Unique website pageviews	45.000
C.2.2	No. of views/ downloads	4.500
C.2.3	Blog posts	125
C.2.4	Total No. of Social media followers;	5.500
C.2.5	No. of newsletter subscribers	1.500

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#	Communication KPIs	Target
C.2.6	Average click-to-open rate	20-30%
C.3	Press Outreach and Event Planning	
C.3.1	Press releases	10
C.3.2	Spotlight on (fireside chats with experts)	15
C.3.3	Participation in media speeches and interviews (tv/radio)	25
C.3.4	Articles in agriculture and industry magazines features	30
C.3.5.	Digital Ag 360° podcast learning series	2x7

Table 7 Communication KPIs for Smart Droplets

Furthermore, the KPIs will be distributed between the three reporting periods (M1-M18, M19-M30, M31-M42) in which the DEC plan will be also updated. This will be a preliminary plan that is foreseen and is subject to change and updated by each deliverable based on projections of the project activities and the scope of each partner. The distribution will be done during upcoming WP meetings.

The reporting mechanism already described in Section 3.3 will help maintain accountability and achieve these targets.

The first reporting period of the project is fundamental for establishing connections and building interest around the project and will be used to:

- Map stakeholders and their needs that must be addressed;
- Develop the project's website, visual identity, communication materials and social media channels;
- Establish and implement the protocol for deciding events, publications and identifying synergies;
- Begin outreach to other projects, and initiatives;
- Participate in events and publish press releases and newsletters;
- Familiarize partners with all communications channels, templates, and protocols.

4.2. Reporting Tools

Event and communication reporting

Partners will be asked to report on their dissemination and communications activities on a monthly basis. Feedback will be collected from partners using an online form as shown below.

Figure 25 Smart Droplets reporting form

Input from the partners will be consolidated and used to monitor DEC progress and make necessary adjustments to the plan, and to hold partners accountable.

5. Exploitation

Smart Droplets will produce several commercial and non-commercial Key Exploitable Results (KERs). This chapter will provide an introduction to these results, potential pathways for their exploitation and KPIs for monitoring their impact. A dedicated **Sustainability, Scalability & IPR management strategy v1** (D6.5) will be developed by M6 to expand upon this initial plan and provide a concrete roadmap for the duration of the project and beyond.

5.1. Key Exploitable Results

Smart Droplets has identified seven key exploitable results that will be available for use/reuse by partners and target groups stakeholders. Figure 26 describes each result, who is responsible for it and who it will benefit.

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Figure 26 Smart Droplets KER

5.2. Exploitation Pathways

All of Smart Droplets currently identified KERs will be openly accessible and available free of charge during the project's lifetime.

AGR and AGC have strong market positions on two dimensions of the market – domestic and international- in the agricultural robotics and artificial intelligence manufacturing sector. These two partners also have strong relationships with valued clients and can act as B2B market representatives for Smart Droplets Solutions. Commercial agreements will be signed between AGC, AGR and all the partners participating in the development of Smart Droplets solution (AUA, WU, EUT, VLF, AFL), however, it is expected that AGC and AGR will continue to develop the Smart Droplets solution (KER1). On the other hand, the Retrofit Kit (KER2) with great commercial exploitation value will be further developed and coordinated by AGC. Whereas the Sprayer with a Direct Injection System will be further developed after the project's lifetime by AGR and AUA.

Based on the expertise of the industrial partners involved (AGC, AGR) and the field experience of AUA, with the support of developments in T6.1 and T6.2 the development of above mentioned potential, commercial exploitable results bring benefits to the project by

- Connect the Smart Droplets solution to producers and farming facilities, thus creating customer reach
- Activating the network effect of the toolkit by gaining access to new stakeholders through a well-developed network
- Financial viability of the toolkit and other KERs will continue to offer free services to the community while others wishing to gain full access to the services will pay a fee to be agreed upon within the consortium in due time

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All KERs will be further examined and evaluated in terms of their potential (commercial, scientific, societal, political) and D6.5 **Sustainability, Scalability & IPR management strategy v1** will provide a detailed plan for each result and outline concrete measures to be taken by the partners. Part of the tools to be used in order to achieve this purpose is the characterization table which will be used in to further evaluate the results. These exploitation pathways mentioned above serve as the basis for upcoming deliverables and effectively can encapsulate the development of the project, its market potential and other important topics related to Smart Droplets exploitation.

Characterization of Exploitable Results	
Market	Who will the customer be and what benefits will they receive?
	What is the anticipated time to market?
	What is the size of the market in M€ and relevant trends?
	What is the approximate price range of this result and price of licenses?
	Who are the competitors?
Steps towards exploitation	How will this result rank against competing products/services in terms of price and/or performance?
	When is the expected date of achievement?
	What are the foreseen barriers to successful implementation?
	What are the costs incurred after the project and before exploitation?
IPR status	Which partners will be involved in results development?
	Have you protected or will you protect this result? How? When?

Table 8 Characterization table for potential exploitable assets

5.3. Exploitation KPIs

The exploitation activities will be regularly evaluated and monitored. A series of KPIs, related to the future exploitation of the project's results have been already defined by the Smart Droplets consortium, as it is described below:

Table 9 Exploitation KPIs and target values

Exploitation KPIs and target values (immediately after the project)	
Performance indicator	Target value
Smart Droplets products/services reaching the market	Up to 7
Contributions to new drafts and/ or technical documents	2
Number of sets of standardization recommendations	2
Number of MoUs/LoIs with industry associations and groups	20

Exploitation KPIs and target values (immediately after the project)	
Number of MoUs/Lols signed with investors and other potential partners	5

6. IPR Management Strategy

Smart Droplets will adopt a comprehensive IP and Innovation Management strategy taking into account all four distinct project stages/phases working in lockstep with the Exploitation Strategy. The phases of the IPR Management Strategy and the corresponding activities are demonstrated at the figure below:

Figure 27 Smart Droplets IPR Management Strategy

1. Project Planning / Proposal Stage: All project participants background, tangible and intangible assets (i.e. scientific studies, methods, materials), and the potential IPRs attached to them (i.e. patent, copyright), likely to be needed for the implementation of the project and/or for the use of the expected results subject to IPR have been already taken under consideration during the proposal formulation. Assets of interest gathered, will be used in order to formulate the first Preliminary Results Ownership List.

2. Grant Preparation: Matters related to management of knowledge and IPR handling (Confidentiality, Background & Sideground IP, Ownership/Joint ownership of results, Legal Protection of results, Exploitation of results and access rights) are defined in the Consortium Agreement (CA). **Results Ownership:** Each participant will own the results it generates. **Joint ownership:** When results are generated jointly, the partners in question will determine their respective share of the innovation and a Joint Ownership agreement will be signed establishing the basis for future exploitation.

3. Project Implementation: Newly generated knowledge/innovations and related new IP, will be constantly recorded and assessed. Overall, the most suitable protection of IP depends on the character of the results. Therefore, it is essential to compile a complete list of the background, sideground and the expected results

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(foreground) of the project to properly manage IP and support the preparation of the exploitation activities, as well as to provide input for the **Results Ownership List** needed for the final periodic report.

This will be done in the form of a preliminary **IP Assessment** (using a questionnaire), a systematic review of the IP owned and brought to the project, IP generated during the project including possible joint IP development and joint ownership. Furthermore, a **tailored and individualized analysis** for each project partner will be implemented resulting in the development of an **individual IP Profiles**. Based on these profiles, we will be able to map and assess the current status of each partner in terms of project innovations, internal processes related to IP management (e.g. internal IP policies, security, as well as an internal IP self-assessment), while we can group project partners in terms of maturity and implement customised actions providing individualised information.

In terms of **IP Protection**, Smart Droplets will establish the tools and mechanisms to facilitate Project Partners to make informed decisions about the potential protection of their IP. Smart Droplets is expected to identify and propose **IP protective measures**, based on project partner's needs, as well as based on different technologies, end-products etc. that will be generated during the project.

Capacity Escalation Activities will also take place including, a preliminary (1st) training session on IP and its relationship with the exploitable results, while individual meetings with project partners (semi structured interviews) will also take place. **Training activities** will also focus on Project specific areas of interest in relation with IP such as Data, AI etc.

4. Project Conclusion: Project partners must be aware that obligations concerning IP management and certain provisions in the agreements remain in force after the project conclusion such as confidentiality obligations, transfer of results, obligations to protect results capable of commercial exploitation. In this context, when approaching the end of the Project, all Project Partners will be informed about their obligations and next steps while will also **verify the Results Ownership List** in the context of the **2nd training session**. All the abovementioned activities will be implemented in the context of **T6.4: Exploitation, sustainability & IPR management** and will be further recored in **D6.5 Sustainability, Scalability & IPR management strategy v1**.

7. Conclusion

D6.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v1, has provided an overview of the communication, dissemination and exploitation phases during the whole project lifetime. The intention of this document is to outline the initial DEC plan which will be implemented during the first period of the Smart Droplets project, as well as the tools that will be utilized in order to reach DEC's KPIs and project's audience.

More specifically, the document covers a wide range of key activities (as well as sets their timelines) to be conducted to meet the dissemination, communication and exploitation targets. All partners will be actively involved in the communication and dissemination of Smart Droplets aiming to assure the proper exploitation of the project's outcomes and maximize the impact.

The second *Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports (v2, D6.2)*, due M12, will be an updated version of the DEC plan. It will evaluate the current plan to identify weaknesses and strengths of the applied activities and tools and establish objectives and concrete actions beyond M12 until the third iteration (M24). The second version will focus on the diffusion of the scientific and technological information generated under the umbrella of the two pilots and emphasis will be placed on sparking interest in the demonstrators and broadening stakeholder engagement with the project activities and results.

Annex A: Logo Variations

Annex B: Banners for Social Media

Annex C: Dissemination and Communication Material

6.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2

6.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2

6.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2

OBJECTIVES	EXPECTED IMPACT
<p>Smart Droplets' main objective is to advance both hardware and software capabilities during chemical applications for resource optimisation and minimisation of chemical waste. It will use existing technologies (TRL 7) developed within our not limited to the agricultural industry to accomplish this vision to deliver a complete system capable of transferring large amounts of data from the field into meaningful information and impactful spraying commands to achieve the Green Deal goals.</p> <p>THE ROAD TO ACHIEVING THE OBJECTIVES INCLUDES:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The innovative use of Intelligent Data Infrastructure and Digital Twins. Introducing a robotic solution for autonomous spraying. Optimizing technologies and demonstrating the Green Deal goals in real-life environments. Community building, synergies, and results exploitation. 	<p>IMPACT 1: Smart Droplets is creating added value in the agricultural industry and its supply chain, by reversing the shift to reduce hazardous agrochemical application. The innovative and sustainable results of Smart Droplets will contribute to the resilience and competitiveness of the EU economy while identifying early opportunities and bottlenecks in the IP and exploitation aspects of such technologies.</p> <p># #Innovative #Sustainable #Resilience #Competitiveness</p> <p>IMPACT 2: Smart Droplets offers the necessary test bench for exploring disruptive technologies that can offer global excellence and reduction of agrochemicals. The leading position of the European industry will be validated through benchmarking of all technological aspects during the project implementation. Moreover, real environment demonstrations will showcase the technological progress made within the project and validate their contribution towards the Green Deal. A comprehensive exploitation strategy will advance the adoption rate of robotic, AI and Data solutions, thereby reinforcing European industry leadership in the digital food supply chain.</p> <p># #Resilience #Sustainable #Resilience #Exploitation</p>

PARTNERS |

- AgriFood@LIFE
- FOODSCALE
- VIZIOTE
- AgriFood@LIFE
- LITHUENIA
- EUROPEA
- FEMAC
- WAGeningen University
- COORINATOR | Ioannis Malouas

Smart Droplets
Accelerating the achievement of EU Green Deal Goals for pesticide and fertilizer reduction through AI, data, and robotic technologies

PARTNERS |

- AgriFood@LIFE
- FOODSCALE
- VIZIOTE
- AgriFood@LIFE
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- COORINATOR | Ioannis Malouas

OBJECTIVES |

Smart Droplets' main objective is to advance both hardware and software capabilities during chemical applications for resource optimisation and minimisation of chemical waste. It will use existing technologies (TRL 7) developed within our not limited to the agricultural industry to accomplish this vision to deliver a complete system capable of transferring large amounts of data from the field into meaningful information and impactful spraying commands to achieve the Green Deal goals.

THE ROAD TO ACHIEVING THE OBJECTIVES INCLUDES:

- The innovative use of Intelligent Data Infrastructure and Digital Twins.
- Introducing a robotic solution for autonomous spraying.
- Optimizing technologies and demonstrating the Green Deal goals in real-life environments.
- Community building, synergies, and results exploitation.

EXPECTED IMPACT |

IMPACT 1: Smart Droplets is creating added value in the agricultural industry and its supply chain, by reversing the shift to reduce hazardous agrochemical application. The innovative and sustainable results of Smart Droplets will contribute to the resilience and competitiveness of the EU economy while identifying early opportunities and bottlenecks in the IP and exploitation aspects of such technologies.

#Innovative #Sustainable #Resilience #Competitiveness

IMPACT 2: Smart Droplets offers the necessary test bench for exploring disruptive technologies that can offer global excellence and reduction of agrochemicals. The leading position of the European industry will be validated through benchmarking of all technological aspects during the project implementation. Moreover, real environment demonstrations will showcase the technological progress made within the project and validate their contribution towards the Green Deal. A comprehensive exploitation strategy will advance the adoption rate of robotic, AI and Data solutions, thereby reinforcing European industry leadership in the digital food supply chain.

#Resilience #Sustainable #Resilience #Exploitation

IMPACT 3: Smart Droplets takes a multi-layer complementary approach to tackle key parts of the supply chain, incorporating different components such as Digital Data Twins, robotics, AI, and Data Platforms to create an optimized spraying solution. The data-centric approach includes historic field data, 3rd party information services, and real-time sensory data of the deployed robotic system. Robust European industrial and technology presence requires strong engagement by stakeholders. Therefore, community and capacity building activities will ensure proper transition and adoption of technologies.

#Innovation #Sustainable #Resilience #Exploitation

Smart Droplets
Accelerating the achievement of EU Green Deal Goals for pesticide and fertilizer reduction through AI, data, and robotic technologies

Call HORIZON-CL4-2021-Flawless September 2021 - 28 February 2024
Project ID: 101019046

6.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2

Accelerating the achievement of EU Green Deal Goals for pesticide and fertilizer reduction through AI, data and robotic technologies.

▶ **AT A GLANCE**

PROJECT TITLE:	Accelerating the achievement of EU Green Deal Goals for pesticide and fertilizer reduction through AI, data and robotic technologies (Smart Droplets)	DURATION:	September 2022 - February 2026 (42 months)
PROGRAMME:	HORIZON-CL4-2021-DIGITAL-EMERGING-01-09	COORDINATOR:	Agricultural University of Athens (AUA), Greece
INSTRUMENT:	HORIZON Innovation action	CONSORTIUM:	9 Partners from six European countries
TOTAL BUDGET:	€2 998 370 00	SOCIAL MEDIA:	

▶ **THE CHALLENGE**

Agricultural environments are characterized by rapid changes, while crop care tasks have always been repetitive, tedious, and potentially hazardous. Consequently, the sector is shifting towards more selective treatment applications to improve the quality and efficiency of chemical spraying. To mitigate environmental pollution and de facto negative implication on human health, there is an urgent need to improve the use of pesticide and fertilizer use. The EU Green Deal has set ambitious targets to reduce the use of pesticide and fertilizers by 2030, which cannot be reached without the use of advanced technologies. AI and Data and robotic advances on SFTs (Smart Farming Technologies) can contribute in fulfilling this ambition bringing benefits in terms of reduced pesticide use, low carbon emissions, low water use, reduced food waste, thus enabling environmental sustainability.

▶ **PROJECT OBJECTIVES**

The Smart Droplets project introduces a novel approach for crop care tasks, by connecting key-technological aspects during open field spraying. Based on the scope of the EU Green Deal and the recently reformed Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), Smart Droplets is committed to advance both hardware and software capabilities during chemical application, in order to meet the sustainability goals. Smart Droplets' solution relies upon critical technological building blocks, that constitute a novel crop care approach through the use of:

-
Data infrastructures
-
Robotic systems
-
AI models
-
Digital twins
-
Direct Injection Spraying (DIS)

smartdroplets.eu

6.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2

Accelerating the achievement of EU Green Deal Goals for pesticide and fertilizer reduction through AI, data and robotic technologies.

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COORDINATOR:	Agricultural University of Athens (AUA), Greece
CONSORTIUM:	9 Partners from six European countries
SOCIAL MEDIA:	 www.smartdroplets.eu

smartdroplets.eu

▶ THE CHALLENGE

Agricultural environments are characterized by **rapid changes**, while crop care tasks have always been **repetitive, tedious, and potentially hazardous**. Consequently, the sector is shifting towards more selective treatment applications to **improve the quality and efficiency of chemical spraying**. To mitigate environmental pollution and de facto negative implication on human health, there is an **urgent need to improve the use of pesticide and fertilizer use**. The EU Green Deal has set ambitious targets to reduce the use of pesticide and fertilizer by 2030, which cannot be reached without the **use of advanced technologies**. AI Data and robotic advances on SF15 (Smart Farming Technologies) can contribute in fulfilling this ambition bringing benefits in terms of **reduced pesticide use, low carbon emissions, low water use, reduced food waste**, thus enabling environmental sustainability.

▶ PROJECT OBJECTIVES

The Smart Droplets project introduces a novel approach for crop care tasks, by connecting key-technological aspects during open-field spraying. Based on the scope of the EU Green Deal and the recently reformed Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), Smart Droplets is committed to advance both hardware and software capabilities during chemical application, in order to meet the sustainability goals. Smart Droplets' solution relies upon critical technological building blocks, that constitute a novel crop care approach through the use of:

- Data infrastructures
- AI models
- Digital twins
- Robotic systems
- Direct Injection Spraying (DIS)

The image shows a 3D rendering of a brochure and a fact sheet. The brochure is open, showing the 'Objectives' and 'Field of action' sections. The fact sheet is titled 'Accelerating the achievement of EU Green Deal Goals for pesticide and fertilizer reduction through AI, data and robotic technologies.' and contains the following information:

Fact Sheet Project Information Smart Droplets Grant Agreement ID: 101075446 Topic: Green agreement - digital Start Date: 1 September 2022 End Date: 28 February 2026		Granting authority: European Commission EU Overall Budget: € 1 319 019,25 EU Contribution: € 599 070,90 Co-financed by AUA (Agricultural University of Athens)
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The brochure also lists the Coordinator (Agricultural University of Athens) and Participants (Wageningen University, FUNDACIO EUROPEA, FUNDACIO VEGEOLAB, FONDACIÓ INNOVACIÓ, FUNDACIÓ INNOVACIÓ, FUNDACIÓ INNOVACIÓ, FUNDACIÓ INNOVACIÓ, FUNDACIÓ INNOVACIÓ, FUNDACIÓ INNOVACIÓ).

6.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2

TITTLE PLACE HOLDER

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TITTLE PLACE HOLDER

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TITTLE PLACE HOLDER

PROJECT DETAILS

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Annex D Partner Social Media Information

6.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2

Affiliation	Partners' social media pages					
	LinkedIn	Facebook	Twitter	SlideShare	YouTube	Instagram
AUA	https://www.linkedin.com/in/agricultural-university-of-athens-ua-ofc-3814321aa/	https://www.facebook.com/AgriculturalUniversityofAthens/	N/A	N/A	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCiRPTax6lrU8I5xY3Fie3g	https://www.instagram.com/agricultural_university_athens/
WU	https://www.linkedin.com/school/wageningenuniversity/	https://www.facebook.com/WUR/	https://twitter.com/WUR	N/A	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCXaytnClAXlaqIngyQh-pWg	https://www.instagram.com/uniwageningen/
EUT	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eurecat/	https://www.facebook.com/Eurecatorg/	https://twitter.com/Eurecat_news	N/A	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCWvIFJ__t_6ozc7bDaKZw	N/A
VLF	https://www.linkedin.com/company/vizlorellc/about/	N/A	https://twitter.com/vizlorellc	N/A	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC0he04pR8q3AFS_X3mKybhQ/videos	N/A
FSH	https://www.linkedin.com/company/foodscale-hub/mycompany/	https://www.facebook.com/foodscalehub/	https://twitter.com/foodscalehub	https://www.slideshare.net/FoodScaleHub	https://studio.youtube.com/channel/UC62UF3dqwrhsZ3xkr9a5dAw?c=UC62UF3dqwrhsZ3xkr9a5dAw	https://www.instagram.com/foodscalehub/
AGC	https://www.linkedin.com/company/agreenculture/	https://fr-fr.facebook.com/people/AgreenCulture/100063791550287/	https://twitter.com/AGC_Robotics	N/A	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCJ369EIE0EJ4MjmjeS5KABQ	https://www.instagram.com/agc_robotics/
AFL	https://www.linkedin.com/company/agrifood-lithuania-dih/	https://www.facebook.com/AgriFood.lt	https://twitter.com/AgriFoodDIH_LTU	N/A	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCxuzLiM7S6CeNPUNLmnX0wQ	N/A
AGROMA SA	https://www.linkedin.com/company/agroma-sa/	https://www.facebook.com/people/Agroma/100064604443017/	N/A	N/A	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCQ5ZhnSkmJDLBK_W3tHUyA	N/A
FEMAC	https://www.linkedin.com/company/cl%C3%BAster-femac/	N/A	https://twitter.com/femac_cat?lang=en	N/A	https://www.youtube.com/@FEMAC100	https://instagram.com/femac_cat?igshid=YmMyMTA2M2Y=